

The School of Commonwealths

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Abstract

The didactic method commonly used in schools to teach students needs to be revised to ensure the highest quality of education. We propose a new model of education based on the didactic-dialectical method, following the model of how the science system operates. Students, following the example of the scientific community, form a global community where each of them reviews each other written assignments specified by the class teachers. In this systemic way, we enhance students' capacities to think critically and cooperate globally.

Keywords: Architectures for educational technology system, Cooperative/collaborative learning, Distributed learning environments, Learning communities, 21st century abilities

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1. Introduction

The dominant teaching method has been didactic, involving the transfer of knowledge from someone who possesses more to someone with less – from a teacher to a student. The didactic method is deeply ingrained in higher education, reflected in dedicated university positions. For instance, Polish universities have roles solely focused on teaching (didactic positions) and others encompassing both research and teaching (research-didactic positions). Despite these efforts, there is still room for improvement in the quality of education to stimulate the development of essential skills needed to navigate a rapidly changing environment. However, we must first ask ourselves a fundamental question about the foundations of the education system: Is a didactic-dominant teaching method truly capable of providing quality education, considering the need to develop skills such as critical thinking and global cooperation, as indicated by UNESCO's report (International Commission on the Futures of Education, 2021)?

Let us compare the higher education and science systems to answer this question. To do so, we pose another question: Would humankind's knowledge have developed to its current level if the science system was based only on the didactic method? Let's imagine such a scenario in which a science system relies solely on this method. In this system, a scientist publishes a scientific article, the content of which cannot be questioned, turning it into dogma. It remains unchallenged because knowledge transfer in the didactic method is unidirectional, flowing from a scientist with more knowledge to a scientist with less. All other scientists follow suit until these dogmas solidify humankind's knowledge. While these achievements could

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¹Pierzchalski, M. (2022). *Szkola Rzeczypospolitych* [Polish version]. In A. B. Kwiatkowska & M. M. Sysło (Eds.), *Informatyka w edukacji* (pp. 128–138). ISBN 978-83-8180-645-9. Wydawnictwo Adam Marszałek. <https://iwe.mat.umk.pl/materials/art2022/16.pdf>. References have been updated to English equivalents where available, and missing references have been added as necessary. Minor stylistic revisions have been made, and the course example has been updated, replacing the original C programming course with a Data Science course example. Supplementary material with three appendices have been added, with Appendix B describing dedicated software developed to support the approach presented in the article.

be helpful and solve specific problems, they would eventually lead to a cessation of development. Thus, the didactic method is not suitable for continuous knowledge development but only for development up to a certain level.

Humankind introduced a two-way transfer of knowledge into the science system to facilitate continuous knowledge development (Spier, 2002). Thanks to this solution, all interested parties can question each other's published content in the pursuit of truth. Our science system is thus grounded on dialectics. In the dialectical method, understood as argumentative dialogue, new knowledge is the product of a discussion between a minimum of two individuals, and its effectiveness is heightened when the participants hold different points of view yet are similar enough to achieve understanding through argumentation. In other words, they are at a comparable professional level within the same area of knowledge.

In the system of publishing scientific knowledge, journals specialize in a particular area of knowledge to increase the efficiency of the dialectical science system (Casadevall and Fang, 2014). For instance, a scientist from Poland published an article in a specialized scientific journal, contributing to the global discourse on the natural laws of star formation. The findings of this scientist are not considered dogma, and anyone can question them. Through the creation of specialized journals in the science system, we have facilitated discussions among individuals at similar levels within the same area of knowledge. Everyone engaged in this discussion shares a common goal – the pursuit of truth.

Science relies on higher education to mold new generations of scientists. In this process, the didactic method plays a pivotal role, as one of its expected results is to shape the students' knowledge to challenge the teacher's knowledge. Having mastered the teacher, students can enter the dialectical science system. Consequently, the higher education and science systems can be viewed as one didactic-dialectical system. The former facilitates the development of individual knowledge to a predetermined level, while the latter ensures the ongoing progression of humanity's knowledge.

The problem with the present approach to shaping students' knowledge might lie in the insufficient stimulation of critical thinking within the higher education system, as the dialectical method is only applied to developing humanity's knowledge. This development is provided by scientists operating in the dialectical science system. They contribute valuable knowledge to humanity by sharing their thoughts in the public domain, often introducing previously unknown facts. The higher education system should therefore stimulate the development of students' ability to question knowledge, in order to more effectively educate new generations of scientists and thereby increase the effectiveness of the scientific system in advancing human knowledge.

2. Problem solution proposition

We propose *The School of Commonwealths* – a didactic-dialectical communication system but focused on the development of individual knowledge – as a solution to the problem described in the previous section. One does not have to be a scientist to make discoveries and develop knowledge. This knowledge is individual, valuable to the person acquiring it but not necessarily to all of humanity. *The School of Commonwealths* places a student in a didactic-dialectical process of individual knowledge development. This system still involves transferring knowledge from the teacher to the student. However, following the scientists' example, students review each other's written assignments.

It might be pointed out that this is what has been happening so far. Students learn from each other after class, solving tasks together and discussing. Humankind's knowledge also developed this way at its beginnings, when scientists locally discussed all sorts of problems. Would humankind's knowledge have developed to its current level if the science system had been based solely on unformalized local interactions between scientists? If so, why are students confined to informal local interactions?

The School of Commonwealths is a global communication system designed to develop individual knowledge, modeled after the global system for publishing scientific articles. Students from anywhere on the globe can discuss with each other and solve various problems. For instance, students from universities in Ukraine and Poland can connect in this way, with no restrictions as long as the content of the classes being connected aligns. In the new system, interactions between students would be formalized by allowing them

Figure 1: The School of Commonwealths – a conceptual model of the system of interaction between students and teachers; white nodes represent students; black nodes represent teachers; thin red edges depict interactions in the virtual classroom; thick gray edges indicate interactions in the physical classroom.

to review assignments to each other. This formalization would elevate these interactions to a higher level. Interactions through written communication are considered more advanced than interactions through speech. For example, information transmitted through speech exists only in a particular time and space, making it non-revisitable. In contrast, communicating through writing is more effective.

The second phrase in the system’s name has two meanings. First, written as one word ‘Commonwealths’ refers to common goods, systems that facilitate cooperation to create common wealths; and second, written as two words ‘common wealths’ refers to any meaning that is shared by a minimum of two people. For example, if two people cooperatively understand the law of universal gravitation, the meaning of this law becomes a common wealth because these two minds share it. Thus, a key element in developing *the School of Commonwealths* is the formation of cognitive bonds through mutual understanding. This arrangement increases the likelihood of building relationships between students following the model of making professional relationships in science. If a minimum of two people understand each other, then, according to the principle of homophily, the probability of building a relationship between them increases (McPherson et al., 2001).

Interactions among students are facilitated in the model through the process of reviewing each other’s assignments. Figure 1 depicts two physical classrooms, exemplified by Taras Shevchenko National University in Kyiv (KNU) and Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń (NCU). Thick dark dashes signify interactions within physical classrooms, where students share the same physical space. Virtual connections between these classes are represented by thin red edges, signifying interactions in the virtual classroom. For students, these interaction involves the exchange and review of assignments. For instance, a KNU student completes a data science assignment and submits it for review. Automatically, another student is chosen from a group of virtually connected classes from both KNU and NCU to review the assignment. Once the reviewer comprehends the content of the assignment, the meaning within the homework becomes a common wealth, as the two minds mutually grasp it. This mode of communication draws an analogy to how the system of publishing scientific articles operates. The reviewer, having understood the article’s content for publication, establishes a cognitive bond with the individual submitting the article as they begin to share the same meaning.

In the proposed model, classes combined virtually operate separately within their respective universities. All that is required is an agreement between teachers regarding the tasks assigned to students. This is depicted by thin red edges connecting teachers, represented by black nodes. There are no restrictions on

establishing interactions, as the model is global, enabling interaction between any university worldwide, provided the content of the classes aligns. Allowing system members to interact creates opportunities to build cognitive and emotional bonds. Students in Ukraine could establish connections with students in Poland, with the principle of homophily at the core of their formation. This is how the global integration of the student community, mirroring the global community of scientists, is achieved in this model.

One can consider the model as another layer of the university's operation. Students are immersed not only in physical classrooms but also in a virtual classroom. In situations where attending a university physically is not possible (due to pandemic or warfare), the virtual classroom can still function, and learning can remain continuous. Another potential disruption to university operation can be the sudden death of a class instructor and related staffing problems. If there were a virtual combination of classes, the death of an instructor, for example, from KNU, would not disrupt the continuity of the class. In this scenario, only the workload of the remaining lecturer from NCU is increased. Such an increase would only occur in extreme cases. The university losing a lecturer could accept the grades from a lecturer from that other university. This approach would ensure the stability of the education system's operation, as demonstrated in this example in Ukraine. By enhancing the stability of this system's operation, we contribute to the security of state operations.

3. Solution implementation proposition

3.1. *GitHub as a collaborative infrastructure*

The proposal to implement the model is based on GitHub, a hosting service for Git repositories and collaborative software development platform commonly used in open-source projects. There are other solutions available on the market, such as GitLab, Bitbucket, and Gitea, but GitHub is the most popular, currently being used by 94 million users worldwide². At the core of GitHub is Git, a distributed version control system, enabling highly efficient software development that requires collaboration among multiple developers (Chacon and Straub, 2014). One of the primary mechanisms GitHub provide for establishing collaboration on source code development consists of two functionalities, i.e., forking and pull requesting. Any publicly available source code repository on such a service can be forked, i.e., copied to one's account along with the origin history. Then, one can make any changes to the code, e.g., solving some identified problem in that code. After making these changes, a pull request for our solution can be exposed to the primary repository. The author who manages the development of the source code in the original repository can accept this solution, return it for correction, or reject it altogether. When it is accepted, we become co-authors of the source code located in the primary repository. This is how globally collaborative development of open-source projects takes place.

3.2. *Implementation*

The new school works similarly – assignments prepared collaboratively by the instructors are uploaded to remote repositories on GitHub. Assignments, prepared in this manner, are made available to students in virtual class previously created by the instructors. This class is part of a virtual organization, which can represent, for example, a university department or course. Each student in such a class forks the provided repository and works individually to solve the problem contained in the task. After completing the task, student opens a pull request to the instructor's repository, and one reviewer is automatically selected³ from the virtual class to check the correctness of the task. After checking the assignment, the reviewer either accepts it or sends it back for correction.

The automatic reviewer selection mechanism on GitHub requires additional configuration. Specifically, a `.github` or `.docs` directory containing a text file named `CODEOWNERS` must be added to the repository with the student assignment. Assigning code ownership to all students allows them to access each other's assignments. While this level of transparency may be considered a disadvantage by some, we argue that fostering openness and trust is beneficial in an educational context.

²Data provided by GitHub <https://octoverse.github.com/>

³The automatic reviewer selection mechanism on GitHub works with 'Team' or 'Enterprise' licenses for a virtual organization. The licenses are paid, but teachers can apply for a discount to get them for free.

Figure 2: An example of the directory structure of a student assignment repository. The ‘.git’ directory and its contents are omitted, as they are automatically created when a local repository is initialized using Git.

Figure 2 illustrates the directory structure of a sample assignment repository for a data science course. The repository is divided into two main parts: laboratory tasks performed during classes (the `lab` directory) and homework assignments (the `hw` directory). The files `hw.css` and `lab.css` are used to style the instructions in HTML format, which are generated from the R Markdown files `lab-hello-r.Rmd` and `hw-pet-names.Rmd`.

Within the `hw.Rmd` file, students are expected to place their solutions, which are subsequently reviewed by their peers. The `CODEOWNERS` file specifies the organization and class responsible for the repository, using a syntax that includes an asterisk and the at sign, for example: `*@my-organization/my-class`. These identifiers must be adapted accordingly; for instance, `*@SOC-2024-DS/SOC-DS` denotes a class belonging to a data analysis course conducted in 2024 (see Table 1 in Appendix C).

Once such a repository is created within a virtual class, it appears under the ‘Repositories’ tab. From there, access rights can be configured using a drop-down menu on the right-hand side. Students must be granted write access by selecting the ‘Write’ permission level.

The final step, performed only once when setting up virtual classes, is to enable automatic reviewer selection. This functionality can be activated in the class settings by navigating to ‘Settings,’ then ‘Code Review,’ and selecting ‘Enable Auto Assignment.’ Since the teacher does not participate in the review process, the option ‘Never assign certain team members’ should be selected, and the teacher’s name chosen accordingly.

The manual configuration of the School of Commonwealths described above can be replaced by the use of a dedicated software, described in Appendix B.

3.3. Interaction dynamics

Figure 3 depicts the interaction structure in the new school during the same task. This structure is formed over time (a video visualization of the described interaction dynamics is provided as supplementary material in Appendix A), and in the figure, we observe the final shape of the structure when all students have interacted with some of their peers. Let’s assume that the time t for forming such a structure is 10. At $t = 0$, we can imagine no edges in Figure 3. The formation of the structure begins with interactions between teachers to develop tasks for students ($t = 1$). This process occurs along the edges labeled ‘Push/Pull’. A ‘Push’ operation involves pushing the local repository to the remote one, while a ‘Pull’ operation means pulling the remote repository to the local one. One teacher, making changes to the tasks locally, pushes them to the remote repository, which the other teacher also co-authors. When one teacher pushes out their changes, the other can download them and make their own or modify earlier ones. Teachers, similar to

Figure 3: The example of the structure of interactions during the execution of a single task; RR – review request, RS – review submitted; Fork – repository fork operation; Push/Pull – push and pull operations to remote and local repositories, respectively.

programmers, collaboratively prepare student tasks in a loop of pushing and pulling. This process concludes when the teachers agree on the final form of the tasks ($t = 2$). This agreement indicates that they share the same meanings contained in the tasks, making these meanings common wealths. These wealths are then shared by the minds of the students. The process of sharing the common wealths by more minds begins with interactions at the ‘Fork’ edges, during which students, whether in physical classes or not, fork a repository with a task ($t = 3$). While the Figure 3 may suggest that the two combined classes are utilizing distinct remote teacher repositories, in reality, they are employing a shared remote repository accessible to all, prepared in advance by the teachers at time $t=2$. After forking the repository, they work on solving the problem within to ultimately understand the conveyed meaning. When the task is complete, the student opens a pull request, and another student is selected from the virtually connected classes to review it. This request is executed on the edges marked ‘RR.’ Associated with each such request is a requirement to write and submit a review, executed on the edges marked ‘RS.’

For example, the cooperation among students could begin with student S11 submitting an assignment for review by student S21 ($t = 4$). Each task has a specific due date, although some students may complete the task earlier than others. In our example, student S11 finished the task the earliest. Subsequently, students S22 and S24 complete the task ($t = 5$), followed by S14 and S21 ($t = 6$). At $t = 7$, the remaining students, namely S12, S13, and S23, send their work for review, and student S21 provides feedback to student S11. The reviewer, S21, assigned to review the work submitted by student S11, must understand the content contained therein. Accepting the work implies comprehending its content, thus the meaning of that content becomes a common wealth as the two minds share it. This is how common wealths become increasingly common as they involve more and more minds. At $t = 8$, additional reviews are submitted from S13 to S12 and from S23 to S24. As before, after the reviewers understand the work, each of the meanings contained therein becomes a common wealth. Then, at $t = 9$, reviews are submitted from S12 to S21 and S11 to S23. The last reviews are submitted from S22 to S13, S14 to S22 and S24 to S14 ($t = 10$). At this final stage, the common wealth is shared by all the minds when all the works are accepted by reviewers. Therefore, we can say that students and a teacher from Poland, as well as students and a teacher from Ukraine, form one Commonwealth in this example.

4. Discussion

Humanity's knowledge is our common wealth. We must make every effort to ensure its continued development. Only by developing without hindrance it has a chance to flourish constantly. To this end, it is necessary to create friendly conditions in universities that enhance students' capacities to think critically and cooperate globally. *The School of Commonwealths* is a proposal for a didactic-dialectical system that emphasizes these. Given that these abilities are a characteristic of scientists, the new school could become a forge of ideas and talents. In this view, it is an extension of the forge concept presented in 1918 by Zygmunt Janiszewski (Janiszewski, 1918; English translation in: Kuzawa, 1968, pp.112-118). As in Janiszewski's case, an essential element of the new system is creating the right work atmosphere by bringing together people with similar interests. *The School of Commonwealths* enhances the ability of students and teachers to create and strengthen ties from the local to the global level. By creating ties, it is by the principle of homophily that the global integration of a community of students occurs along the lines of the global community of scientists. In 1920, Zygmunt Janiszewski, together with Waclaw Sierpiński and Stefan Mazurkiewicz, introduced to the world the then most momentous form of bringing together people with similar interests on a global scale – *Fundamenta Mathematicae* (Przeniosło, 2009). This was the world's first mathematical journal with a narrow specialization, which enabled global interaction between scientists specializing in selected areas of mathematics. Thus, it increased the efficiency of the dialectical science system at the time. *The School of Commonwealths* follows this example and provides opportunities for global interactions between students in selected areas of knowledge. Interactions between students are taken to a higher level – from informal local interactions to formal global ones through writings, along with how the knowledge exchange system between scientists works.

The School of Commonwealths could significantly impact the transformation of university teaching methods, responding to UNESCO's call for the development of a new social contract for education (International Commission on the Futures of Education, 2021). The innovation in the proposed method of inter-university integration lies in the creation of the *The School of Commonwealths*, which could contribute to a global systemic shift from a didactic model to a didactic-dialectical model. Similar to how Janiszewski's system proposal contributed to the flourishing of mathematics in Poland (Duda, 2013), the *The School of Commonwealths* could contribute to the flourishing of knowledge across all Commonwealths.

5. Supplementary Material

Appendix A: Video simulation (`soc_simulation.mp4`).

Appendix B: GH-SOC GitHub CLI extension for managing the School of Commonwealths

Appendix C: Course schedule template (Table 1).

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